

GURUKUL BUSINESS REVIEW (GBR)

An International Refereed Management Journal of FMS, Gurukula Kangri Vishwavidyalaya, Haridwar.

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FROM THE DESK OF THE EDITOR

Greetings and Best Wishes,

I take this opportunity to thank all contributors and readers for making Gurukul Business Review (GBR) an astounding success. The interest of authors in sending their research based articles for publication and over whelming response received from the readers is duly acknowledged. I owe my heartfelt gratitude to all the management institutes for sending us their journals on mutual exchange basis, and their support to serve you in better way.

I am happy to place the 10th issue of GBR academic journal with the impact factor of 0.65 rated by GSSR. The present issue incorporates the following articles :

- 1- Microfinance services in developing countries: A proactive approach to poverty reduction.
- 2- An aerial glimpse of workplace deviance in indian service industry.
- 3- Corporate social responsibility for market integration & sustainable development: An overview.
- 4- Gender preference by parents: An empirical study on rural and urban India.
- 5- Impact of demographic variables on organizational commitment and job satisfaction.
- 6- Study on consumer satisfaction towards branded consumer non durables: A study with reference to rural consumers in Kerala.
- 7- Decision making style of students enrolled in professional and non-professional courses: A comparative study.
- 8- A sociocultural examination of gender role: A study of projection of women in advertisements.
- 9- Financial supply chain management: Issues & challenges.
- 10- Buying decision of rural consumers: A study on Dehradun district.
- 11- Financial crisis and gold's performance: A way towards progress or stress.
- 12- Sustainability development in India: The user prospect.
- 13- An empirical study of customer satisfaction in the banking industry.

As the editor, I also want to thank the authors, the university administration, board of editorial advisors, reviewers and my editorial members for their contributions that has really made the journey to complete uninterrupted 10 years in publication. For more information on our editorial or the journal statistics or call for papers or any other aspects of the journal, please visit our website at www.gkv.ac.in

Thank you for your time and consideration. Be our partners and make this journal part of your life of ideas, thoughts and practice. Happy reading.

I remain,

(V.K. Singh)

GENDER PREFERENCE BY PARENTS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON RURAL AND URBAN INDIA

Bimal Jaisawal*
Namita Srivastava**
Sushma***

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ABSTRACT

In India we have very rich cultural background but there are some loopholes too. These socio cultural factors forces married women to have a male child; economic conditions have very less influence here. Because of which number of females are reducing and the situation is becoming poor to worst day by day specially in some of the states like Haryana, Rajasthan, and Punjab. This is our general belief that only the literacy and education can change the human mentality that only males can run the family or society but our study shows that there is very less correlation (0.16 only) between sex ratio and literacy, which can be very dominantly seen from the census report as well. Also study shows that sex ratio is lower in case of urban India (902) where literacy is high as compared to rural India (919) and there is negative correlation between urban sex ratio and urban female literacy, means on increasing literacy of urban females the sex ratio is decreasing, which is a very shocking situation. The reason behind is when people become literate they become aware about the use of technology as well and its easy availability of such technology in urban areas again motivate them to go for prenatal examinations and then after sex determination they have the option to go for sex selection. The broadness

of this problem can be easily understood by the examples of some states like Rajasthan where in a village, 8 brothers have to marry with one girl because of non availability of any girl in their village for marriage. Whereas on the contrary in states like Kerala we have very good sex ratio of 1084 females over 1000 males. The reason is not only literacy but also the proper implementation of law against female feticide as well.

KEYWORDS: Sex ratio, Literacy, Socio-cultural Factors, Son Preference, Trend and Female Feticide.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of "Agle Janam Mohe Bitiya Na Kijo" still has a firm base in India due to various socio cultural and economic factors. The families in India still prefer male child to be a part of their families because of their cultural beliefs and rituals. There are various cases of females being tortured by their in-laws because of not having any boy child as they still feel that they are living in a male dominated society and only males can do everything. This type of mentality is one of the basic reasons behind day by day decreasing male female sex ratio in India.

The difference in sex ratio especially in India is because of the social cultural beliefs. Females are still believed to be "ParayaDhan" that to be transferred to someone else that's why they are not assumed to be a part of family. Again they don't have the right to be a part of their parent's final rituals; hence parents are desirous of a male child in their family to do at least their final rituals as well as to move on their family further.

People still don't want a girl child to be born again and again in their family. They are being treated as unwanted even if they are born. According to Mother Teresa "Biggest disease today is not leprosy or tuberculosis, but rather the feeling of being unwanted". We have reached to the heights of moon but the tragedy is this; that in some of the areas we are still in the loop holes. In the words of Pundit Jawaharlal Nehru "You can tell the condition of a nation by looking at the status of its women".

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Gender equality is more than a goal in itself. It is a precondition for meeting the challenges of reducing poverty, promoting sustainable development and building good governance.

-Kofi Annan

Sex ratio is defined as the number of females per 1000 males in the population and is an important social barometer to measure the extent of prevailing ratio between males and females in a society at a given point of time. It may be noted that the sex ratio is expected to be almost at parity in nature. In India, sex ratio is skewed in favour of males and has continued to rise.

Changes in sex composition largely reflect the underlying socio-economic and cultural patterns of a society in different ways. A preference for sons or for more sons than daughters has been documented in several countries in the world. Preference for male children is especially prevalent in South Asia, East Asia and North Africa, while in many European and Latin American countries; a balanced sex composition of children is more commonly preferred.

In India, in particular, son preference is very strong and pervasive and has been frequently cited as one of the major obstacles for reducing the national fertility level. According to this argument, if couples continue to bear children in order to have a minimum number of desired sons, they would exceed the two-child family norm advocated by the national family planning program. Earlier studies conducted in India, however, have not found any consistent evidence linking son preference with fertility behaviour.

It is natural believe that males and females in the population exactly balance each other. Around the year 2000 (As given in table below), the world had around 986 females against 1000 males. Also it was evident that except Indonesia and Japan, the other Asian countries show low sex ratios. It is interesting to note that the sex ratio in U.S.A., Indonesia, Russian Federation and Japan has always remained above unity for the last half a century. The most dramatic decline of about 200 points in the sex ratio is seen in the Russian Federation. In U.S.A., it has shown as improvement from 1002 to 1029 in the last fifty years. Bangladesh has shown a continuous improvement in its sex ratio to reach from 880 in 1950 to 953 in 2000. Pakistan and China have also shown an improvement.

Thus among the major nations of the world, India is the only exception. According to the Census of India, 2001, the sex ratio stands at 933 for the country

as a whole. This is a welcome improvement from the 1991 Census, which had recorded 927 females for every 1000 males. The sex ratio in the country had always remained unfavourable to females. Moreover, barring some hiccups, it has shown a long term declining trend. The sex ratio at the beginning of the twentieth century was 972 and thereafter showed continuous decline until 1941. In 1951 there was a marginal increase of one point, but thereafter it again dropped for two consecutive decades to reach 930 in 1971. In fact, between 1961-71, the country saw the sharpest decline of 11 points in the sex ratio. Thereafter, it has fluctuated marginally around 930 in successive censuses.

Country Wise Sex ratio (Year 2000)

India	933
Pakistan	938
China	944
Bangladesh	953
World	986
Indonesia	1004
Nigeria	1016
Brazil	1025
U.S.A.	1029
Japan	1041
Russian Fed.	1140

Source: World Population Prospects (midyear estimates) 1998 revision, Volume 2, Sex and Age, United Nations.

If we talk about the latest trends the situation is still not very satisfying. As per Census 2011, total population of India is 1,21,01,93,422 which comprises of 62, 37, 24,248 males and 58, 64, 69,174 females with the sex ratio of 940 females per 1000 males. As per Census 2011, highest sex ratio states are Kerala (1,084) followed by Pondicherry (1,038), Tamil Nadu (995), Andhra Pradesh (992) and Chhattisgarh (991). Whereas five states which have the lowest sex ratio are Daman & Diu (618), Dadra & Nagar Haveli (775), Chandigarh (818), NCT of Delhi (866) and Andaman & Nicobar Islands (878).

Sex ratio, India

1901	972
1911	964
1921	955
1931	950
1941	945
1951	946
1961	941
1971	930
1981	934
1991	927
2001	933
2011	940

Several reasons seem to explain the consistently low levels of sex ratio and their further decline in the country. Some of the important reasons commonly put forward are listed below:

- Neglect of the girl child resulting in their higher mortality at younger ages.
- High maternal mortality.
- Sex selective female abortions.
- Female infanticide.
- Change in sex ratio at birth.

Easy accessibility to technology usage nowadays plays a role of icing on the cake to again deprive the situation of females as it is easily predetermined that the baby to be born is male or female and can be easily aborted. The imbalance in the number of males and females begins in the beginning. It is now a well established law of nature that the males exceed females at the time of birth. It is believed that generally 943-952 female births take place for every 1000 male births, which in effect would mean that there is a deficiency of about 50 females per 1000 males in every birth cohort.

The overall sex ratio of India is dependent on the sex ratios obtained in different States and Union territories and their relative weights in terms of size of population. The diversity in sex ratio among the States and Union territories is phenomenal.

This is also evident from data available at the Census of India, 2001, the sex ratio among the major States ranged from 861 in Haryana to 1058 in Kerala. In 1991 also, Haryana with a sex ratio of 865 was at the bottom with Kerala 1036 at the top. The changes in sex ratio over time, therefore, are dependent on the changes in the ratios of the individual States and Union territories and their relative share in population.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the gender preference among parents of different states in India.
- To make an analysis of mental differentials in urban and rural India for preference of child sex.
- To study role of literacy in gender preference in urban and rural India.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The study done by S Puri, V Bhatia, HM Swami about Gender preference and awareness regarding sex determination among married women in slums of Chandigarh shows that in the age group of 20-35 years married women belonging to poor

socioeconomic groups residing in rural & slum areas shows desirability for male child. Sample of 373 women is representative of 35000 slum population which is catered by Urban Health Training Centre was taken.

The study shows majority (57.8%) of them intended to have male as their first child & 14.4% wanted second child too as male even with the first male baby. Three-fourth women wanted to have their third baby as boy after two baby daughters and 6% wanted a boy even after two baby boys. Similar kind of preference has been observed in different parts of the country evident from studies of Mumbai, Himachal Pradesh and other states.

The study done by Indira Dey (Pal) and Ramendra Narayan Chaudhuri about gender preference in rural areas of West Bengal revealed that among mothers with one living child, all the mothers with a daughter and no son desired for another child and wanted that child to be a boy. Whereas of the mothers with only one son, 8.7% did not want another child and 43.5% of them desired another son and the remaining (47.8%) wanted a daughter. Among mothers with two or three living children, the proportion of mothers not desiring any more children increased with the increase in the number of living sons. Among mothers with three living children, all the mothers with three daughters desired for a son, but none of the mothers with three sons desired for a daughter although the number of mothers in each subgroup was small. Above parity four, the mothers did not show any desire for any more children irrespective of the gender composition of the children. Therefore, 39.2% of mothers wanted a son in their next pregnancy, while only 8.3% of mothers wanted a daughter in future.

The study by Swarna S. Vepaon gender equity observes the changes over the period to conclude whether the overall gender gap is increasing or declining. The indicators used in this study to compute the gender gap. Index include-

- (i) Workforce participation ratio and labor force participation ratios
- (ii) Incidence of unemployment
- (iii) Type of employment held
- (iv) Wage rates for casual employment
- (v) Levels of literacy of adults and children
- (vi) Life expectancy at age one
- (vii) Infant mortality rates, and
- (viii) Juvenile sex ratio.

These indicators are combined for sub-indices. Seven sub indices are calculated to capture the gender gap: (i) Literacy index, with literacy rates at various educational levels and school attendance ratios, (ii) Adult illiteracy index that gives the incidence of illiteracy among adult men and women above the age of fifteen, (iii) Work participation index of all the three types of worker population ratios, (iv) Unemployment index with the three types of unemployment of usual status, weekly status and daily status, (v) Employment quality index with persons holding regular employment and wages for casual workers, (vi) Child labour index that combines the child labour in the two age groups of 5-10 and 10-14 yr, and (vii) Health index consisting of child survival and life expectancy. Child survival has two components of juvenile sex ratio and infant mortality. The final gender gap index presented in this article has been calculated for two points of time, in the nineties and twenties.

This study of Rashmi Sharma, S Mukherjee on comparative study of selected parameters of gender discrimination in rural versus urban population of Ahmadabad, Gujarat explores Gender Discrimination as prevalent in both areas and is evident by alarmingly low sex ratio (SR) among urban under fives (562), high USG rates in urban especially in educated ones. Low education and high dropouts (female), poor quality/quantity jobs, low contraceptive uses reveal gender discrimination in rural population. Main causes of non-use of contraceptive - "husbands do not want or "desire for son" summarizes the scene in rural and urban areas respectively. More women and men everywhere preferred male children.

Shelley Clark in his study on son preference and sex composition shows that "Although the effect of son preference on sex composition of children ever born is undetectable in national-level estimates that aggregate across all families, this article provides empirical evidence from India that son preference has two pronounced and predictable family-level effects on the sex composition of children ever born. First, data from India show that smaller families have a significantly higher proportion of sons than larger families. Second, socially and economically disadvantaged couples and couples from the northern region of India not only want but also attain a higher proportion of sons, if the effects of family size are controlled".

The study by Fred Arnold, Minja Kim Choe & T.K. Roy states "India is a country with a pervasive preference for sons and one of the highest

levels of excess child mortality for girls in the world (child mortality for girls exceeds child mortality for boys by 43 per cent).

The demographic effects of family composition are estimated with hazard models. The analysis indicates that son preference fundamentally affects demographic behaviour in India. Family composition affects fertility behaviour in every state examined and son preference is the predominant influence in all but one of these states. The effects of family composition on excess child mortality for girls are more complex, but girls with older sisters are often subject to the highest risk of mortality".

Rohini P. Pande in her study examines the role of the sex composition of surviving older siblings on gender differences in childhood nutrition and immunization, using data from the National Family Health Survey, India (1992-1993). Logit and ordered logit models were used for severe stunting and immunization, respectively.

The results show selective neglect of children with certain sex and birth-order combinations that operate differentially for girls and boys. Both girls and boys who were born after multiple same-sex siblings experience poor outcomes, suggesting that parents want some balance in sex composition. However, the preference for sons persists, and boys who were born after multiple daughters have the best possible outcomes.

The research done by Nan Marie Astone and Rohini P. Pande on son preference in rural India, explains demographic manifestations of son preference, particularly in rural India. Socio economic and socio cultural variables are also considered in the study. It was examined that whether predictors of son preference differ by desired family size or not?

The analysis shows that women's education, particularly at secondary and higher levels, is consistently and significantly associated with weaker son preference, regardless of desired family size. Also social norms, such as marriage customs, caste and religion, are included, economic wealth and women's employment at household or village levels are not significant. Among social factors, caste and religion are associated with son preference but, once state of residence is controlled for, marriage patterns and cultivation patterns are insignificant. The strength and significance for son preference of many determinants differs by desired family size.

The results suggest that policy makers seek to influence son preference, need to identify and target different policy levers to women in different fertility and social contexts, rather than try an approach of one size that fits all.

The study done by Robert Repetto on Son Preference in developing countries analyzed data from Jordan, Bangladesh, and India and observed that fertility decisions were not influenced by a desire for sons. He argued that couples base their fertility decisions lie on the economic benefits and costs of children and not on their sex.

Repetto suggested that couples who already have sons may desire more children because of the perceived financial benefits associates with having sons, while couples with more daughters may restrict their childbearing because of the perceived economic burden associated with having several daughters.

The study by Gary H. McClelland emphasizes to explain the positive association between the number of boys and fertility is that despite a strong preference for male children, couples with many female children may not risk having an additional child because of the fear that the child may be another girl.

Thus, if couples take this risk factor into consideration when making their fertility decisions, couples who have many daughters would be more likely to restrict future childbearing than couples who have many sons. The methods commonly used to assess the effect of sex preferences on fertility are inadequate to the task. Parity progression ratio analyses suffer from logical problems stemming from the heterogeneity of sex preferences and the riskiness

As per the study conducted by Mallika A. Bhagyalaxmi (2009) on Effect of socio-the sex preference in Ahmadabad district, a number of cultural and socio-economic factors influence the relative benefits and costs of sons and daughters and ultimately affects the parents' gender preferences.

The study was conducted among 385 married women in the reproductive age group of 15-49 years during March 2007-April 2008 in randomly selected areas of Ahmadabad district, Gujarat, India. Son-preference was observed amongst 87.53 per cent of the studied women. 93.04 per cent of the illiterate women preferred

male child whereas 68.75 per cent of the women who completed graduation had the preference for son.

The association between education and son preference was found to be statistically significant ($P < 0.01$). The son preference observed more in rural areas (94.30%) than urban areas (80.73%) and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). Keeping the family line (42.14%) and the girl not staying with parents after the marriage (50.45%) were the major reasons for son preference.

The study found that education, place of residence and cultural factors play a role in son-preference.

MACRO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF TRENDS IN SEX RATIO

1. Sex ratio trend of last one century

Year	Sex Ratio
1901	972
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2001	933
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Source: Census of India.

The trend shows that sex ratio is continuously declining since from 1901 from 970 females per 1000 males to 940 females per 1000 males in the year 2011. The situation was alarming in the year 1991 and since then government had started focussing on increasing awareness about this problem. Now the graph is on increasing node because of strict laws against female feticide as well as increasing literacy and awareness about pros and cons of sex selection.

Several reasons seem to explain the consistently low levels of sex ratio and their further decline in the country. Some of the important reasons commonly put forward are listed below:

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This study of Rashmi Sharma, S Mukherjee on comparative study of selected parameters of gender discrimination in rural versus urban population of Ahmadabad, Gujarat explores Gender Discrimination as prevalent in both areas and is evident by alarmingly low sex ratio (SR) among urban under fives (562), high USG rates in urban especially in educated ones. Low education and high dropouts (female), poor quality/quantity jobs, low contraceptive uses reveal gender discrimination in rural population. Main causes of non-use of contraceptive - "husbands do not want or "desire for son" summarizes the scene in rural and urban areas respectively. More women and men everywhere preferred male children.

Shelley Clark in his study on son preference and sex composition shows that "Although the effect of son preference on sex composition of children ever born is undetectable in national-level estimates that aggregate across all families, this article provides empirical evidence from India that son preference has two pronounced and predictable family-level effects on the sex composition of children ever born. First, data from India show that smaller families have a significantly higher proportion of sons than larger families. Second, socially and economically disadvantaged couples and couples from the northern region of India not only want but also attain a higher proportion of sons, if the effects of family size are controlled".

The study by Fred Arnold, Minja Kim Choe & T.K. Roy states "India is a country with a pervasive preference for sons and one of the highest

levels of excess child mortality for girls in the world (child mortality for girls exceeds child mortality for boys by 43 per cent).

The demographic effects of family composition are estimated with hazard models. The analysis indicates that son preference fundamentally affects demographic behaviour in India. Family composition affects fertility behaviour in every state examined and son preference is the predominant influence in all but one of these states. The effects of family composition on excess child mortality for girls are more complex, but girls with older sisters are often subject to the highest risk of mortality".

Rohini P. Pande in her study examines the role of the sex composition of surviving older siblings on gender differences in childhood nutrition and immunization, using data from the National Family Health Survey, India (1992-1993). Logit and ordered logit models were used for severe stunting and immunization, respectively.

The results show selective neglect of children with certain sex and birth-order combinations that operate differentially for girls and boys. Both girls and boys who were born after multiple same-sex siblings experience poor outcomes, suggesting that parents want some balance in sex composition. However, the preference for sons persists, and boys who were born after multiple daughters have the best possible outcomes.

The research done by Nan Marie Astone and Rohini P. Pande on son preference in rural India, explains demographic manifestations of son preference, particularly in rural India. Socio economic and socio cultural variables are also considered in the study. It was examined that whether predictors of son preference differ by desired family size or not?

The analysis shows that women's education, particularly at secondary and higher levels, is consistently and significantly associated with weaker son preference, regardless of desired family size. Also social norms, such as marriage customs, caste and religion, are included, economic wealth and women's employment at household or village levels are not significant. Among social factors, caste and religion are associated with son preference but, once state of residence is controlled for, marriage patterns and cultivation patterns are insignificant. The strength and significance for son preference of many determinants differs by desired family size.

The results suggest that policy makers seek to influence son preference, need to identify and target different policy levers to women in different fertility and social contexts, rather than try an approach of one size that fits all.

The study done by Robert Repetto on Son Preference in developing countries analyzed data from Jordan, Bangladesh, and India and observed that fertility decisions were not influenced by a desire for sons. He argued that couples base their fertility decisions lie on the economic benefits and costs of children and not on their sex.

Repetto suggested that couples who already have sons may desire more children because of the perceived financial benefits associates with having sons, while couples with more daughters may restrict their childbearing because of the perceived economic burden associated with having several daughters.

The study by Gary H. McClelland emphasizes to explain the positive association between the number of boys and fertility is that despite a strong preference for male children, couples with many female children may not risk having an additional child because of the fear that the child may be another girl.

Thus, if couples take this risk factor into consideration when making their fertility decisions, couples who have many daughters would be more likely to restrict future childbearing than couples who have many sons. The methods commonly used to assess the effect of sex preferences on fertility are inadequate to the task. Parity progression ratio analyses suffer from logical problems stemming from the heterogeneity of sex preferences and the riskiness

As per the study conducted by Mallika A. Bhagyalaxmi (2009) on Effect of socio-the sex preference in Ahmadabad district, a number of cultural and socio-economic factors influence the relative benefits and costs of sons and daughters and ultimately affects the parents' gender preferences.

The study was conducted among 385 married women in the reproductive age group of 15-49 years during March 2007-April 2008 in randomly selected areas of Ahmadabad district, Gujarat, India. Son-preference was observed amongst 87.53 per cent of the studied women. 93.04 per cent of the illiterate women preferred

male child whereas 68.75 per cent of the women who completed graduation had the preference for son.

The association between education and son preference was found to be statistically significant ($P < 0.01$). The son preference observed more in rural areas (94.30%) than urban areas (80.73%) and the difference was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). Keeping the family line (42.14%) and the girl not staying with parents after the marriage (50.45%) were the major reasons for son preference.

The study found that education, place of residence and cultural factors play a role in son-preference.

MACRO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF TRENDS IN SEX RATIO

1. Sex ratio trend of last one century

Year	Sex Ratio
1901	972
1911	964
1921	955
1931	950
1941	945
1951	946
1961	941
1971	930
1981	934
1991	927
2001	933
2011	940

Source: Census of India.

The trend shows that sex ratio is continuously declining since from 1901 from 970 females per 1000 males to 940 females per 1000 males in the year 2011. The situation was alarming in the year 1991 and since then government had started focussing on increasing awareness about this problem. Now the graph is on increasing node because of strict laws against female feticide as well as increasing literacy and awareness about pros and cons of sex selection.

2. State wise sex ratio for the according to census 2011.

State	Sex ratio
A & N Islands*	878
Andhra Pradesh	992
Arunachal Pradesh	920
Assam	954
Bihar	916
Chandigarh*	818
Chhattisgarh	991
Dadra & Nagar Haveli*	775
Daman & Diu*	618
Delhi*	866
Goa	968
Gujarat	918
Haryana	877
Himachal Pradesh	974
Jammu & Kashmir	883
Jharkhand	947
Karnataka	968
Kerala	1084
Lakshadweep*	946
Madhya Pradesh	930
Maharashtra	925
Manipur	987
Meghalaya	986
Mizoram	975
Nagaland	931
Orissa	978
Puducherry*	1038
Punjab	893
Rajasthan	926
Sikkim	889
Tamil Nadu	995
Tripura	961
Uttar Pradesh	908
Uttarakhand	963
West Bengal	947

Source: Census of India 2011.

According to census 2011, state wise sex ratio shows that among states of India (except union territories) states with lowest sex ratio are: Punjab (893), Uttar Pradesh (908), Bihar (916), Gujarat (918), Arunachal Pradesh (920), Maharashtra (925), and Rajasthan (926). However states with highest sex ratio include Andhra Pradesh (992) Tamil Nadu (995) and Kerala (1084).

3. Preference of son and daughter according to male and female parents

State	Want More Sons		Want More Daughters	
	Female	Male	Female	Male
Andhra Pradesh	9.3	12.0	2.6	2.0
Arunachal Pradesh	28.3	30.3	5.0	3.2
Assam	24.1	17.9	2.1	2.8
Bihar	39.2	38.5	1.2	1.7
Chhattisgarh	32.8	24.8	3.6	2.4
Delhi	11.7	11.7	2.1	1.5
Goa	8.7	11.4	4.1	2.1
Gujarat	22.7	20.0	2.3	1.6
Haryana	22.0	18.4	1.2	2.2
Himachal Pradesh	11.8	9.2	2.0	1.1
Jammu & Kashmir	23.4	23.9	3.1	2.2
Jharkhand	28.1	24.6	2.3	3.7
Karnataka	11.6	12.7	4.6	2.7
Kerala	11.0	11.8	5.7	3.8
Madhya Pradesh	30.8	27.9	1.8	1.0
Maharashtra	14.1	14.3	2.9	2.2
Manipur	28.5	34.7	4.2	3.3
Meghalaya	11.9	21.5	17.0	13.5
Mizoram	29.0	43.5	22.7	14.7
Nagaland	21.4	28.4	9.8	5.0
Orissa	24.2	20.3	2.4	1.6
Punjab	17.7	13.4	1.6	1.5
Rajasthan	34.3	24.0	1.5	1.8
Sikkim	15.5	17.1	5.9	4.2
Tamil Nadu	5.7	7.9	3.1	1.8
Tripura	17.7	15.2	3.4	2.2
Uttar Pradesh	33.5	27.8	1.7	1.2
Uttarakhand	20.7	13.6	2.1	1.3
West Bengal	16.5	16.6	3.5	2.1
India	22.4	20.0	2.6	2.0

Source: National Family Health Survey-3 Reports.

Source: National Family Health Survey-3 Reports.

The graph clearly shows that son preference is much higher as compared to daughter preference both in males as well as females. Highest daughter preference is seen in the states of Mizoram and Nagaland both in males as well as in females, the main reason behind is again socio cultural factors in eastern states of India, where women situation is equivalent to that of males. There is no dowry system, so there is no mental pressure on parents of girl child.

4. Change in population of females over one decade

Year	2001	2011	Difference
Total	494,828,644	810,341,220	315512576
Rural	359,817,177	405,170,610	45353433
Urban	135,011,467	181,298,564	46287097

Source: Census of India 2001 and 2011.

From the above graph it is shown that ratio of increase in rural female population is very high as compared to total increase in urban female population over last one decade. The above figure shows that in the year 2001, 72.7% of total female population was constituted of rural females and remaining 29% population is of urban females. In the year 2011, 50% of total female population is constituted by rural females however only 22.3% of total population is constituted of urban females.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based on empirical research. For analysis secondary data is being used from census of India surveys and National Family Health Surveys. Data for Sex ratio of various states of rural and urban India is used and an analysis is performed on its relativity with literacy in these regions.

India/State/Union Territory #	Population		Population		Child Sex Ratio			Literacy Rate			
	Male		Female		Rural	Urban	Total	Males		Females	
	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban				Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
A & N ISLANDS #	130,647	71,683	113,764	63,850	975	947	878	88.53	92.96	79.58	85.79
ANDHRA PRADESH	28,219,760	14,290,121	28,092,028	14,063,624	942	946	992	70.24	85.99	52.05	75.02
ARUNACHAL PRADESH	554,304	165,928	514,861	147,518	964	944	920	68.79	89.45	53.78	79.04
ASSAM	13,689,739	2,265,188	13,090,777	2,123,568	957	955	954	76.51	91.84	64.09	85.71
BIHAR	47,983,851	6,201,496	44,091,177	5,528,113	935	906	916	71.90	84.42	50.82	72.36
CHANDIGARH #	17,155	563,127	11,849	462,555	862	867	818	86.68	90.65	74.17	81.55
CHHATTISGARH	9,792,514	3,035,401	9,811,144	2,901,137	972	932	991	78.20	91.63	55.40	77.65
DADRA & NAGAR HAVELI #	98,250	94,928	84,774	64,901	961	878	775	78.18	94.81	51.36	84.86
DAMAN & DIU #	32,317	117,783	28,014	64,797	925	903	618	89.71	91.95	71.97	82.94
DELHI # 2011	227,000	8,749,410	192,319	7,584,506	809	868	866	90.04	91.05	74.03	81.10
GOA	276,121	464,590	275,293	441,719	924	917	968	91.71	93.47	76.84	84.96
GUJARAT	17,802,975	13,679,307	16,867,842	12,033,504	906	852	918	83.10	92.44	62.41	82.08
HARYANA	8,791,036	4,714,094	7,740,457	4,107,494	831	829	877	83.20	89.37	60.97	77.51
HIMACHAL PRADESH	3,102,262	371,630	3,065,543	317,074	909	878	974	90.48	93.72	75.33	88.66
JAMMU & KASHMIR	4,809,619	1,855,942	4,325,201	1,558,164	860	854	883	75.51	84.90	53.36	70.19
JHARKHAND	12,775,468	4,156,220	12,261,478	3,773,072	952	904	947	74.57	89.78	49.75	76.17
KARNATAKA	19,010,998	12,046,744	18,541,531	11,531,431	945	941	968	77.92	90.54	59.60	81.71
KERALA	8,403,706	7,617,584	9,051,800	8,314,587	960	958	1084	95.29	96.83	90.74	93.33
LAKSHADWEEP #	7,228	25,878	6,893	24,430	888	915	946	95.06	96.40	88.66	88.13
MADHYA PRADESH	27,142,409	10,470,511	25,395,490	9,589,155	917	895	930	76.64	90.24	53.20	77.39
MAHARASHTRA	31,593,580	26,767,817	29,951,861	24,059,714	880	888	925	86.39	93.79	67.38	85.44
MANIPUR	966,264	403,500	933,360	418,632	929	945	987	84.14	92.05	69.95	80.21
MEGHALAYA	1,194,757	297,911	1,174,214	297,125	972	957	986	72.83	93.17	69.45	89.49
MIZORAM	271,319	281,020	257,718	280,957	966	978	975	88.35	98.67	80.04	97.54
NAGALAND	724,595	301,112	682,266	272,629	932	979	931	79.49	92.11	72.01	88.10
ORISSA	17,584,859	3,616,819	17,366,375	3,379,305	939	909	978	80.41	91.83	61.10	80.70
PUDUCHERRY #	194,388	416,097	199,953	434,026	957	969	1038	88.49	93.80	73.82	84.60
PUNJAB	9,086,466	5,548,353	8,230,334	4,839,083	843	851	893	77.92	87.28	66.47	79.62
RAJASTHAN	26,680,882	8,939,204	24,859,354	8,141,572	886	869	926	77.49	89.16	46.25	71.53
SIKKIM	242,122	79,539	213,840	72,187	952	917	889	85.42	92.94	73.42	85.19
TAMIL NADU	18,663,701	17,495,170	18,525,528	17,454,559	937	957	995	82.08	91.82	65.52	82.67
TRIPURA	1,385,505	486,362	1,324,546	474,619	955	945	961	90.86	95.80	80.06	91.38
UTTAR PRADESH	81,044,655	23,551,760	74,066,367	20,918,695	904	879	908	78.48	81.75	55.61	71.68
UTTARAKHAND	3,512,456	1,641,722	3,513,127	1,449,447	894	864	963	87.63	89.78	66.79	80.02
WEST BENGAL	31,904,144	15,023,245	30,309,532	14,110,815	952	943	947	79.51	89.15	66.08	81.70
INDIA	427,917,052	195,807,196	405,170,610	181,298,564	919	902	940	78.57	89.67	58.75	79.92

India/State/ Union Territory #	Literates			No of Literates			
	Rural	Urban	Total	Male		Female	
				Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
A & N ISLANDS #	293695	183863	109832	1476	771	1430	744
ANDHRA PRADESH	51438510	30850648	20587862	401762	166184	539712	187465
ARUNACHAL PRADESH	789943	557105	232838	8058	1855	9573	1866
ASSAM	19507017	15988262	3518755	178927	24665	204256	24776
BIHAR	54390254	46478818	7911436	667369	73460	867595	76397
CHANDIGARH #	809653	20217	789436	198	6212	160	5672
CHHATTISGARH	15598314	11173237	4425077	125224	33127	177096	37362
DADRA & NAGAR HAVELI #	228028	102355	125673	1257	1001	1651	765
DAMAN & DIU #	188974	43281	145693	360	1281	389	781
DELHI #	12763352	300539	12462813	2521	96095	2598	93520
GOA	1152117	420523	731594	3011	4970	3583	5199
GUJARAT	41948677	21896928	20051749	214236	147980	270275	146607
HARYANA	16904324	10393591	6510733	105661	52748	126955	52993
HIMACHAL PRADESH	5104506	4533373	571133	34287	3965	40695	3576
JAMMU & KASHMIR	7245053	4898008	2347045	63695	21860	81057	22199
JHARKHAND	18753660	12973765	5779895	171322	46293	246462	49535
KARNATAKA	41029323	22860653	18168670	243981	133054	311100	141126
KERALA	28234227	14595727	13638500	88191	78670	99755	89088
LAKSHADWEEP #	52914	11352	41562	76	268	78	277
MADHYA PRADESH	43827193	28991005	14836188	354155	116030	477359	123907
MAHARASHTRA	82512225	41703097	40809128	365709	285402	444522	281598
MANIPUR	1891196	1268881	622315	11484	4383	13343	5219
MEGHALAYA	1817761	1345805	471956	16405	3197	16907	3320
MIZORAM	847592	368672	478920	3071	2848	3220	2880
NAGALAND	1357579	904799	452780	9116	3269	9475	3095
ORISSA	27112376	21669993	5442383	218690	39386	284229	41875
PUDUCHERRY #	966600	284931	681669	2197	4436	2709	5130
PUNJAB	18988611	11195395	7793216	116613	63570	123820	60777
RAJASTHAN	38970500	26945543	12024957	344314	100260	537500	113820
SIKKIM	449294	326398	122896	2834	856	2913	847
TAMIL NADU	52413116	24752447	27660669	227384	190538	282746	211135
TRIPURA	2831742	2016022	815720	15249	5077	16544	5194
UTTAR PRADESH	118423805	88396557	30027248	1032679	288095	1331889	291834
UTTARAKHAND	6997433	4670901	2326532	40083	18286	52600	18114
WEST BENGAL	62614556	39898187	22716369	401260	168516	458679	172715
INDIA	778454120	493020878	285433242	5446316	2183642	6896521	2268501

For doing research three hypotheses are assumed and are tested against a fixed significance level.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The following hypotheses are assumed and are tested against a fixed significance level. The results are as follows:

Hypothesis 1:

H₀: There is no difference between means of urban sex ratio and rural sex ratio.

H₁: There is difference between means of urban sex ratio and rural sex ratio.

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
URBANSR	35	912.54	41.33	6.99
RURALS	35	922.63	43.04	7.28

One-Sample Test

Test Value=0					
	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference
					Lower Upper
URBANSR	130.614	34	.000	912.54	898.34 926.74
RURALS	126.821	34	.000	922.63	907.84 937.41

Tabulated Value: 2.03

Observed Value: 130.614

Observed value is greater than tabulated value, hence null hypothesis is REJECTED.

Inference: Our null hypothesis is rejected means alternative hypothesis is accepted. It means there is difference between means of urban sex ratio and rural sex ratio in India. Therefore there is difference between mentality of people of rural and urban India about the preference of sons. However its very surprising that rural sex ratio is rationally higher as compared to urban sex ratio.

Hypothesis 2:

H₀: There is no difference between means of urban literacy and rural literacy.

H₁: There is difference between means of urban literacy and rural literacy.

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
RURALLIT	35	2.2E+07	27727083.98	4686733
URBANLIT	35	1.4E+07	18813211.07	3180013

One-Sample Test

	Test Value=0					
	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
RURALLIT	4.746	34	.000	22241546	1.3E+07	3.2E+07
URBANLIT	4.430	34	.000	14086311	7623747	2.1E+07

Tabulated Value: 2.03

Observed Value: 4.746

Observed value is greater than tabulated value, hence null hypothesis is REJECTED.

Inference: Our null hypothesis is rejected means alternative hypothesis is accepted. It means there is difference between means of urban literacy and rural literacy and this difference in literacy is going to affect sex ratio in rural and urban India.

Hypothesis 3:

H₀: There is association between rural sex ratio and rural female literacy.

H₁: There is no association between rural sex ratio and rural female literacy.

Test Statistics

	Rural sex ratio	Rural female literacy
Chi-Square ^{a,b}	4.857	.000
df	30	34
Asymp.Sig.	1.000	1.000

- 31 cells (100.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 1.1.
- 35 cells (100.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 1.0.

Tabulated Value: 47.0

Observed Value: 4.857

Observed value is less than tabulated value, hence null hypothesis is ACCEPTED.

Inference: Hypothesis is accepted and it says that there is association between rural sex ratio and rural female literacy. It means the rural sex ratio is affected by the literacy of especially females of rural area; hence to increase sex ratio of rural areas, government should focus on policy formulation so as to literate the girls of rural and underdeveloped/undeveloped areas.

Correlation between sex ratio and literacy

	SEX RATIO	LITERACY
SEX RATIO Pearson Correlation	1.000	.160
Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.357
N	35	35
LITERACY Pearson Correlation	.160	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	.357	.
N	35	35

Inference: There is a positive and low degree correlation of 0.160 between sex ratio and literacy that shows that these two factors are dependent on each other. Positive correlation shows that as literacy increases the sex ratio also increases. It means we can get rid of this problem through making more and more people literate, but very low degree of correlation shows that there is very low ratio of literacy as influential factor in sex ratio.

Correlation between urban sex ratio and urban female literacy

	Urban Sex ratio	Urban female literacy
Urban sex ratio Pearson Correlation	1.000	-.144
Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.410
N	35	35
Urban female literacy Pearson Correlation	-.144	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)	.410	.
N	35	35

Inference: There is negative and low degree correlation between urban sex ratio and urban female literacy. This result is very surprising as in urban areas it says that as literacy increases sex ratio decreases.

The reasons behind is that as females are becoming more and more literate they are becoming more aware about the use of technology and hence are involved in more sex selection activities. Again in urban areas working women are wishing only one child and hence they wish to have baby boy only because of socio-cultural factors. This was the reason behind decrement in sex ratio in china as well after one child policy.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- **Myth:** There is no difference between the mentality of parents of rural and urban India.
- **Truth:** Son preference in the parents of rural and urban India differs.
- **Myth:** As literacy increases the sex ratio also increases rapidly.
- **Truth:** On increasing literacy the increase in sex ratio is very less, approximately 0.16
- **Myth:** In urban areas if females will become more and more literate then sex ratio will increase.
- **Truth:** There is negative relationship between urban female literacy and sex ratio.
- **Myth:** There is high son reference in case of rural population as compared to urban population.
- **Truth:** Census 2011 shows that 50% of total female population is constituted of rural females however only 22.3% of total population is constituted of urban females.

CONCLUSION

Continuously decreasing sex ratio is a problem for our nation, especially when the facts are so shocking. Government thinks that when we literate female of urban areas they will become aware about the problems and will help in finding solution but the situation is opposite to it, they are contributing more and more towards the selective abortion activities and are involved in decrement in sex ratio.

The solution of this problem can not be done only by increasing the awareness among people but there should be some strict actions taken by the government against such crime. We have laws against the pathologies involved in such crime but what about parents? The fine amount is very less on doing such crime. If parents want this, then pathologies have no choice because they have demand so first demand should be depleted and for this there should be proper and strict action against such parents, then only we can get rid of this problem and improve our overall sex ratio.

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